

Talented Children in the Spirit of Tradition

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Abstract: *The study aims to demonstrate the spiritual, cultural, and gastronomic heritage of the town of Cigánd and to identify the efforts made to preserve and transmit these traditions to future generations. In the introduction of the paper, the authors give a brief theoretical overview of the concepts of tradition and cultural heritage, followed by a definition of the purpose and definition of the transmission of culture and tradition. They then present the traditions and values of the town of Cigánd and the activities, institutions and organizations that help to preserve these traditions. Additionally, the authors draw attention to how the past can be embodied in the present, how it is possible to keep the values created in the past alive, and how people can pass them on to future generations. How can the interest of today's children and young people in our past awaken? The authors discuss the tools needed to keep traditions alive, so young people do not lose interest in today's modern, innovative world. Finally, the efforts of the various institutions in the city are presented to preserve and pass on traditions, with a particular focus on the importance of nurturing and promoting talent and the opportunities it offers.*

Keywords: tradition, heritage, preservation of tradition, talent, talent management, Hungarian Talent, Cigánd

Tradition, cultural heritage, transmission of tradition

Tradition has many meanings, the simplest definition being ‘traditum,’ which means that the past passes on something of the present, passed on from generation to generation. This can be any aspect of society, whether it is an object, an idea, an image of people and events, a practice, an institution, a building, a monument, a landscape, a sculpture, a painting, or a book. What remains of a custom is initially only a memory, a record of a particular time. Later, the adopted image may become a tradition, which, in turn, is the past living in the present (Shils, 1987).

According to *Klaniczay* (1976), tradition is defined as the collective experience and value transmission of humanity, constantly interacting with development and innovation. Tradition is thus the accumulated experience of the past that is embodied repeatedly in the present. Keeping tradition alive is of paramount importance for the cohesion of a community because it serves as a strengthening factor. Cultivating tradition increases a sense of belonging to a community and is the most crucial factor in increasing and maintaining national bonds. It helps to strengthen the sense of belonging to the country. Therefore, the cultivation, preservation, and transmission of traditions are permanent tasks, as are the collection and preservation of values. It is also essential to educate people so that society perceives it as a public responsibility to protect, nurture and promote memories and traditions throughout the country. The cultivation of traditions is crucial, since it documents progress and change (Klaniczay, 1976).

However, this has only sometimes been the case. In the past, the idea of change and progress rejected the cultivation of tradition, as it focused on innovation and improvement, and tradition was criticized and became a target for progressive thinking. Science and tradition conflicted because they were set against each other as opposites. Modern ideas and innovation are increasingly displaced traditional ideas. Tradition was identified with ignorance. Social scientists also paid little attention to tradition, but some recognized it had a far more significant role to play, which must be addressed. However, initially, only ethnographers and historians paid more attention to the role of tradition (Shils, 1987).

Fortunately, this is no longer the case; quite the contrary. Tradition and its transmission are playing an increasingly significant role in smaller as well as larger communities. Some communities are almost sustained by tradition alone. Tradition is not only the roots but also the future, the heritage that can be passed on to the next generation.

Heritage is part of identity. It is a message from the past, made worthy of its authenticity, to be presented to the public. It defines identity and can be understood as remembrance. The concept of heritage is followed by the emergence of architectural heritage and then the concept of cultural heritage. The definition of this concept had to wait until 1985 when the Council of Europe created it. Heritage is interpreted differently at continental, national, local, or regional levels. Although it is a universal concept, this does not mean that different actors in society understand it in the same way, i.e., it varies from one level of analysis to another. Heritage preservation is a fundamental objective. Cultural heritage is also found at local, regional, national, and continental levels, but also at international levels. Cultural heritage is a set of objects or intangible things that have an

important meaning for a community: collected, preserved, restored, examined, when necessary, deciphered, exhibited, and displayed. The aim is to preserve cultural identity and promote sustainable development. Considering the principle of sustainable development, it is necessary to increase the number of cultural heritage sites. Cultural heritage has recently become part of the dynamic development of tourism and a tourist destination (Sonkoly, 2000).

In a broad sense, culture is used in all aspects of life, such as housing, schooling, hygiene, dress, celebration, entertainment, and traditions. The situation is like traditional culture, which has many interpretations. In Hungary, however, it is accepted to mean folk culture, folk art, traditional peasant culture and art. Folk art is understood to mean art that predates the actual history of art. Folk art is used to refer to folk crafts. Hungary's aspiration for national identity has drawn attention to folk art (Abrakovits, 2005).

Many are concerned about heritage and its relationship with the past. The value of traditions lies in the possibility of breaking away from the past, hence the importance of conscious preservation and protection (Fejős, 2005). We distinguish three categories of cultural heritage, which are:

1. Culture, the expressions of traditional ways of life whose manifestations are embedded in physical forms. E.g., religious rites.
2. Individual and collective expressions which have no physical form, such as language, oral poetry, folk songs, or traditional music.
3. The symbolic and metaphorical meanings surrounding the objectification comprise the material heritage (Fejős, 2005).

The essence of tradition is that it already existed when it was taken over and handed down. It is the transmission of tradition itself, when we receive something that was created and practiced in the past and pass it on, that is, a series of variations of values received and passed on. Tradition may change in the transmission process, in many ways, but its main elements remain. What its guardians consider most important in it remains unchanged. A tradition cannot recreate itself; only people can recreate or modify it. The purpose of the modification is to improve the tradition, which can be explained by the desire to create something better in the transmission process. Something must be handed down through at least three generations to be considered a tradition. However, tradition is not just repeating ideas and creations in successive generations; traditions are handed down with normative intent. As a guiding pattern, this normative intention links past and present and then future generations (Shils, 1987).

Nowadays, whether at the local, regional, county, or national level, there is a growing emphasis on the search for and preservation of traditions, the revival of forgotten traditions, and their transmission. More educational establishments are introducing traditionalism, whether in the context of different subjects, at the institutional level, in talent workshops or in the framework of various specialized groups. It is becoming increasingly important to familiarize the younger generation with the past, so they have someone to pass it on to repeatedly. The revival of historical traditions and the development and preservation of a sense of identity are not just a matter of celebrating our national holidays but also of paying more attention to local culture and heritage from an early age.

The cultural heritage of Bodrogköz region

Bodrogköz is a flat area between the rivers Bodrog and Tisza. It is in the northeastern corner of Hungary, on the Slovak Ukrainian-Hungarian border. It is divided by the Hungarian Slovak border, and the part of it that became part of Czechoslovakia in the Treaty of Trianon is called Upper Bodrog, while the Hungarian part is called Lower Bodrog. At present, twenty-two settlements belong to Hungary and another thirty-three to Slovakia. At the mayor's initiative of the town of Cigánd, the fifty-five municipalities have joined forces in an extraordinary way to implement joint programs and create common cultural values. The Town Day event in 2021, entitled "Without Borders in Bodrogköz" - a meeting of Bodrogköz settlements, formalized this cooperation, when the Trianon monument by Sándor Czigándi Varga, a sculptor born and raised in Cigánd, was inaugurated, and ten of his public works can now be seen in the town.

Research has shown that the Hungarian language is becoming endangered in diaspora communities in countries neighboring Hungary, with the number of speakers declining and the majority language gaining ground. This fact makes language preservation and the cultural and linguistic maintenance of bilingual communities a necessity, and to this end, the preservation of traditions, the preservation of Hungarian identity, and the development and transmission of the identity of future generations of Hungarian origin are a priority (Palotai et al., 2019). On 20 December 2022, Hungarians living abroad visited Bodrogköz Museum (Bodrogközi Múzeumporta) in the "Diaspora program" framework. Members of the group arrived from Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Macedonia, and Australia. The guests tasted the HÍR trademark products, had an insight into folk music and folk dance, visited the exhibitions and participated in handicraft activities (source: Bodrogköz Museum, www.muzeumporta.hu).

Bodrogköz region is rich in natural values and attractions, spiritual wealth, and the environment left by our ancestors. Mágócsi Castle in Pácin, built in the 16th century in Renaissance style, and the churches in Bodrogköz region, including Reformed Church of Cigánd, built in the 18th century in Gothic style, are the most important examples of the built heritage. Several villages in Bodrogköz also have country houses or village museums, which are monuments of traditional folk architecture. A complex of buildings in Cigánd called Bodrogköz Museum is of particular importance, which displays the rich peasant culture. A rich archaeological heritage preserves the culture of the conquerors. The former cemetery of the conquistadors in Karos is the site of Archaeological Park of the Age of Conquest, and the first archaeological park in the country, Berzseny village, was in Kisrozvágy. However, there are also numerous monuments, statues, and carvings commemorating the importance of the monuments in Bodrogköz region, as well as numerous cultural events to mark the occasion. Dance and folk culture, local folklore, folk costumes, and gastronomy are also significant. These play a leading role in shaping, developing, maintaining, and preserving the cultural identity of local communities (Kútvölgyi & Viga, 2010).

In each of the settlements of Bodrogköz, we can find places of interest that connect us with the past, or we can meet older people who can tell us about it, even about events of historical significance or importance for the settlement. They are worthily preserved in the settlements. Through close cooperation between local authorities and educational establishments, children not only learn about their past, the customs and traditions of the people of the past from their parents but also learn about them through educational activities and through the institutional education they receive so that even very young children can learn about the folk tales, folk songs, dances and spiritual heritage that their great-grandparents, great-great-grandparents and grandparents have left them.

Traditions, spiritual, cultural, and gastronomic heritage of Cigánd

Cigánd is the only town in Bodrogköz, the center of Cigánd district. The first written record of the settlement dates to 1289. In 1347, the settlement was divided by a land dispute, creating Small and Great Cigánd, separated by a single street. The village council, with the agreement of the inhabitants, decided in 1922 to unite the two villages, which the Ministry of the Interior approved, but the unification was not completed until 1923. The situation lasted for years and was resolved after an extended period, and the village was again unified (Hajdú, 1997).

Cigánd became a town in 2004 but still retains its rural character. It is a town in constant development, but innovation is still a matter of tradition. A powerful sense of local or national identity is also vital to the town's events and the new material goods it creates. The town's administration and inhabitants are committed to preserving and promoting the region's culture.

Cigánd's spiritual and cultural heritage is vibrant. At the same time, its traditions are still alive today. Their transmission is equally essential for all those living in Cigánd. The cultivation of these traditions is a continuous local initiative, which is a thoughtful and organized process. The cultivation of national tradition is not based on a central principle. However, as Gábor Klaniczay (1976) put it on local initiatives and self-activity, tradition is a living force, not a collection locked in a glass case. Preserving tradition is an ongoing process linked to anniversaries and the care of values through celebrating anniversaries.

When it comes to collection and preservation, it is essential to mention the name of *Mihály Kántor*, who played a significant role in the survival of the costume and folk traditions of Cigánd. Mihály Kántor (1885-1968), a scholarly folk teacher of Bodrogköz, came to Cigánd as a preceptor, i.e., assistant teacher, after graduating from State Teachers' College in Sárospatak, and became a teacher in 1905. For half a century, he instructed children, but he was a dominant personality of the whole settlement. He was enthusiastic about collecting material on the history and ethnography of Bodrogköz, made the textile art of the village famous throughout the country, and founded the local dance company, which helped to preserve the folk song and dance culture (Kútvolgyi & Viga, 2010). His work "Flax and hemp works, weavings of Bodrogköz" still preserves all the justly

famous weaving techniques of Cigánd. Bodrogek Landscape Museum Foundation has preserved the book for future generations through the second edition of the work, published in 2002 (Kántor, 2002).

The costume of Cigánd is also worth mentioning, as it was richly decorated and sumptuous. The evolution of the dress of the people of Cigánd can be divided into two significant periods, the first being the period of dressing in folk costume, which covers the period before the First World War, and the second the period of the emergence of urban dress and the abandonment of traditional dresses (the so-called 'undressing') and its transition to a costume. The latter ended in the 1960s when the last people wearing the costume died. The aesthetic value of the costume of Cigánd lies in its modesty, clean lines, harmony despite the lack of colours, and modest decoration despite its richness. The men's black or green shawl dress was decorated with tiny silk roses. Women's dress varied in different ages. Older women wore a plain brown or black skirt with a barely decorated waist. Younger women, on the other hand, wore various embroidered dresses. The girls' hair was braided with coloured silk ribbons, and the daughters-in-law wore coloured silk scarves on their heads (Katona, 2014).

Nowadays, folk costumes are an indispensable part of stage folk dance performances, and this is how they have been preserved for posterity and how new generations have come to know and wear them since folk dance has a long tradition in Cigánd. Children learn folk costumes and folk dancing very closely at preschool age. The name of Cigánd Folk Traditions Nursery School (Cigándi Néphagyományórzó Mesteróvoda) is no coincidence. Folk games, costumes, weaving and dancing, permeate the children's everyday life. Folk dancing is an extracurricular activity in primary school, and wearing folk costumes during performances teaches students to learn about, cherish, and respect traditions. Later, talented dancers became members of Sarkantyús Folk Dance Ensemble, a living history.

The first data on the dance life of Cigánd dates to 1905. At that time, May, or green branch march (májusjárás or zöldágjárás) was mentioned as a musical dance parade, which is still a tradition. The first folk dance group in Cigánd, called Búzavirág, was founded in 1931. In 1934, they joined the Gyöngyösbokréta movement. This brought the dances of Cigánd to attention and made them a research target. Edit *Kaposi* (1999), an eminent researcher of the settlement's dances, authored her doctoral dissertation in 1947, entitled *Dance in Cigánd in Bodrogek*, the most complete summary of the subject to date. Subsequently, several authors published on the subject (Darmos, 2014).

The Gyöngyösbokréta movement organized village dance groups between 1931 and 1944 to make villagers recognize the value of their culture. In the towns and villages where Gyöngyösbokréta folk dance groups were formed, folk dance and folk costume knowledge were more intensively preserved than in villages without such traditional movement. The Gyöngyösbokréta movement has significantly increased the value of local traditions (Abrakovits, 2005).

The most prosperous folk tradition in dance life was the wedding ceremony, where people danced and sang songs until the morning after the rituals (Darmos, 2014). This tradition is also maintained, and great emphasis is placed on its transmission. The revival of the folk wedding

dance is an essential part of the choreography of the folk-dance troupe, together with the costumes, and these inherited rituals are also regularly performed at city events.

Calendar festivals also provided an opportunity to dance. The most memorable, linked to the tradition mentioned above, still preserved today, was the May Day procession, known as the May march or the green branch march. It is held every year in the municipality. A characteristic feature is the girls' dance in front of the church. The girls march through the village - now the town - in a fixed order, accompanied by singing and carrying branches decorated with ribbons and scarves. After the parade, a dance was also held on other occasions, such as Christmas, New Year's Eve, New Year's Day, Carnival, Easter, after the harvest, St. Stephen's Day, and the harvest. They also organized balls, for example, on Catherine's Day (Darmos, 2014). Balls are also a surviving "custom".

In Cigánd, from the mid-19th century, Csárdás was danced as a couples' dance. There are no earlier records, but it is unknown when it was first developed and how it evolved. However, the first sources refer to it as Cigánd hard csárdás, the name of a whole dance process. Within the Csárdás, a Hungarian solo and a couplet were distinguished. Hungarian solo was a dance for men, and the couples' dance was one in which the men let go and figured alone. Csárdás was danced using different holding techniques, such as Csárdás step, variations of the bokage, and turns. Dancing with instruments was not considered aesthetically pleasing and was therefore not used. In the 20th century, new-style dances formed the bulk of the traditional repertoire. For entertainment, the lads put on spurs. The dances were decorated with taps, varied tap variations, clapping, rich figuration such as boxing, fancy variations, and foot-tapping figures.

Traditional dances in Cigánd underwent a meaningful change, becoming less and less ornate over time, and the richly decorated dances were only danced on stage performances. The older people still like to dance Csárdás, and young people also know and like it thanks to the dance groups. Dance films have been preserved of traditional dances in Cigánd, preserving the tradition and providing an opportunity to pass on the dances (Darmos, 2014). Dance groups of different ages regularly participate in city events and national qualifying competitions.

In the traditional dance culture, dance was learned spontaneously, as children saw it from their parents and learnt it. The first dance school was founded in Cigánd in 1911. In 1931, under the organization of Mihály Kántor, the village's young people started to learn the old dances. Until 1934, as a member of Wheat Flower Association (Búzavirág Szövetség) and later joining the Gyöngyösbokréta movement, they reached many places to show their talents and dancing skills and promote the traditions of Cigánd. After Mihály Kántor's retirement, they kept the dance movement alive. Csaba Ureczky, a physical education teacher who came to the village in 1963, organized a new ensemble in the village of teachers under the name Zemplén Dance Ensemble. The dance ensemble was intended to continue the dance traditions of Bodroghköz and other regions. Among their choreographies was, of course, Csárdás of Cigánd. In 1965, Zemplén Children's Dance Ensemble was founded, and children came to the force. The group, founded and taught by *István Nagy*, became at the forefront of the children's dance movement, spreading the love of dance throughout the

country and keeping the love of dance alive in the village, preserving the old dance repertoire, and reviving the customs (Nagy, 2006). The dance ensemble celebrated its 60th anniversary in 2023.

Folk dance education plays a vital role in preschool and primary school education. It provides a new generation for the Sarkantyús Folk Dance Ensemble and Cigánd Children's Folk Dance Ensemble, dance groups formed by local young people and former folk-dance children. They raise the standard of the city's events, are nationally recognized, and have received numerous awards and distinctions.

If we talk about dance, we cannot leave out Sándor Román, a native of Cigánd, who has made the town famous for his dancing activities and talent, and we can be proud of him. Sándor Román is a dance artist, choreographer, theatre director, merited artist, founder of the ExperiDance Company, currently the director of Sándor Román Dance Academy and Sándor Román Entertainment Dance Company, not least a perpetual member of the Company of Immortals and the only living honorary citizen of the town of Cigánd. His parents were traditional folk dancers of the Gyöngyösbokréta movement, from whom he inherited his love of dance. He started his dance studies in Cigánd in Zemplén Children and Youth Dance Company in the 1960s. As an ensemble member in the summer of 1978, he attended the XI World Youth Meeting in Havana. Also, that year, he, and the dance company took part in the television finals of the folk-art contest "Röpülj, páva!" (Nagy, 2006).

Another boom in folk dancing began with the formation of amateur folk music groups. The genuine revival of folk culture came with the television program "Röpülj páva!" in the 1960s when talented singers, musicians, and bands were allowed to show the actual value of folklore. The dance hall movement of the 1970s followed this. These efforts to save our musical heritage changed the face of folk culture (Abrakovits, 2005).

Currently, Sőregi House of Bodrogekőz Museum offers virtual dance classes with Sándor Román, where you can learn the basics of the Cigánd hard csárdás. Sándor Román and his company are regular participants in the town's events, where they dazzle the audience with their dance performances and make the people of Cigánd proud. On 28 December 2022, Krisztián Oláh, Mayor of Cigánd, and Sándor Román signed a public service contract in a ceremony, under which Sándor Román became the official travelling ambassador of Cigánd hard csárdás. The Cigánd csárdás is a national treasure in the Collection of Hungaricums and the Hungarian Register of Values.

In addition to dancing, music and folk instruments, such as the zither, which is still used in Cigánd, also appeared. Its tradition is preserved by Csárdás Zither Orchestra (Csárdás Citerazenekar) and Traditional Choir (Hagyományőrző Énekkar), who, under the leadership of Dezső Téglás, retired school director, have done a remarkable job of preserving and perpetuating the use of the folk instrument and the folk songs of Cigánd. They are taught at the Széptan Primary School of Arts in Cigánd for interested children and young people, and in addition to dancing, they are regular participants in instrumental performances.

Bodrogekőz Museum, which has a rich history, has already been mentioned. In 1943, Mihály Kántor tried to create a house in Cigánd, in Rákóczi Museum of then-Borsi Castle. He started to collect objects, but

unfortunately, none of them survived. Later, in 1987, thanks to the primary school collection, a temporary exhibition was set up in the judge's house in Kiscigánd. The more valuable items were returned to their owners. At the same time, the smaller objects of daily use were transferred to the kindergarten, where an ethnographic exhibition still preserves the memories of the period. Over the years, the exhibition has continued to grow. On 20 August 2000, as part of the millennium celebrations, the new Village Museum was inaugurated in Cigánd, which presents the village's traditions, history, and folk art. Village Museum, which was then established on an enthusiastic local patriot's initiative, began reviving the peasant culture of Cigánd as a rich collection. Thanks to the villagers' donations, two thousand ethnographic objects were quickly built up. With the support of the local government and Rákóczi Museum in Sárospatak, the museum was housed in an abandoned building in the center of the village, which was restored to its original state. Its present form results from reconstruction, with several alterations in the 20th century. The village museum has four rooms and two exhibition rooms. The former comprises two interiors, the clean room, and the atrium, while the latter houses the weaving and local history exhibitions (F. Tóth, 2004).

2015 was another milestone in the life of Cigánd in the spirit of preserving its traditions. In the Slovak Hungarian cross-border project "Dialogue of Museums" framework, Bodrogek Museum was inaugurated and has continuously expanded. Sőregi House has been built next to Village Museum building, and an extensive complex of buildings has been created. The museum complex has become a natural attraction in Bodrogek region, hosting various events, noteworthy events, school trips, fairs, catering, and dance festivals. It is a worthy way of preserving our past and introducing it to the younger generation. The area has several open-air theatres, two children's playgrounds, a lookout tower, a vegetable garden, a beekeeper, and several ovens. Interactive exhibitions, created in the spirit of innovation, make visiting them exciting for children and young people.

Sőregi House is named after the cantor of the village and his son, the former director of the Déri Museum. It is a long house with a village porch and a thatched roof. The building houses a permanent exhibition of the natural geography, history, farming, society, culture, folk art, and dance of Bodrogek. It also houses an exhibition room dedicated to the work of Mihály Kántor. The cellar under the house is a temporary exhibition space where other valuable works from the past and present find a home and then move on - a permanent exhibition of dances, costumes, and the dancing past of Cigánd (MMO, 2016).

In 2021, House of the Past was inaugurated. In 2022, Teachers' House was opened, which houses the temporary exhibition "From Grass to Weaving" and a museum-educational workshop. Thus, Bodrogek Museum, which currently has three permanent and two temporary exhibitions, will be an educational center. Recently, it has become a base institution for traditional education in Bodrogek region. It has excellent relations with educational institutions and cooperates effectively with other organizations. Today, it is not only a place of recreation for children and pupils from local institutions but also a place of camps and school trips visited from all over the country and beyond the border. It offers various programs based on folk traditions, handicraft activities, folk games, and gastronomic experiences.

It is also the venue for the city's cultural open-air events, such as the green branch march, the Béles Festival, the City Day, the St. Martin's Day celebrations, the St. George's Day parade, the winter bonfire, the Sőregi Memorial Meeting, and many other events.

2015, Bodrogek Museum was named "Museum of the Year" in the Pulszky Society - Hungarian Museum Association competition. This award was given for its role in the community, exemplary long-term development, and a spectacular, modern, permanent exhibition of the whole Bodrogek region. Also, this year, it won the special "Exhibition of the Year" award for the permanent exhibition of Sőregi House. In 2021, it won the "Exhibition of the Year" award for the permanent exhibition of House of the Past (<http://www.muzeumporta.hu>). Bodrogek Museum is an actual community space, a permanent venue for large-scale regional events, fairs, and festivals, and a prime destination for cultural tourism in the region.

As the gastronomic experience has already been mentioned above, it is essential to underline that Cigánd is rich in gastronomic values. Many of its dishes have been awarded the HÍR trademark, the "Traditions-Tastes-Regions" (Hagyományok-Ízek-Régiók) trademark. The HÍR trademark is a program established by the Ministry of Agriculture in 2010 to give quality labels to agricultural products and foodstuffs of traditional and regional character in Hungary, guaranteeing the traditional and regional character of the product. The following products are eligible to use the HÍR trademark: small pastie ('cigándi apróbéles'), cabbage with porridge ('cigándi kásákáposzta'), drawn pastie with cabbage ('cigándi nyújtott káposztás béles'), yeast pastie with cabbage ('cigándi kótt káposztás'), corn pie ('cigándi görhe'), cookies ('cigándi linzer'), saligot doughnut ('cigándi sulyom') and leaf fat pastry ('cigándi hájas') (Nagy, 2021). Beyond these, however, many traditional Gypsy dishes are prepared at Bodrogek Museum and in the homes of the townspeople, thanks to the passing on of heritage. No event in Cigánd can be organized without these dishes. „Bodrogek Tájmuzeumáért” Foundation, which has been operating since 2000, with its volunteers, contributes significantly to preparing these products for special occasions and events. In addition to being an outstanding public benefit organization, the Foundation has helped to build and furnish Bodrogek Museum, collect materials, and make Village Museum Bodrogek Museum; in recent years, it has also placed greater emphasis on traditional folk gastronomy and the transmission of regional flavours. All the conditions for preparing traditional folk dishes are provided at the portal. The Foundation's volunteers participate in regional, county, and national events, representing the town and promoting its gastronomic traditions and folk culture. The Foundation has received numerous awards and prizes since its founding. The Foundation has been responsible for the publication of several publications, such as the replica of the book by Mihály Kántor - mentioned above - entitled "A bodrogekzi flax-és kendermunkak, szőttesek" (The flax, hemp works and weavings of Bodrogek), or the already cited recipe book entitled "Bodrogekzi ételek" (The dishes of Bodrogek) (Nagy, 2021). The latter of which was created to preserve and pass on to future generations the recipes of traditional folk dishes representing the old flavours.

It is not only the HÍR trademark that guarantees that Cigánd has preserved its beautiful values since it is not only its recognized gastronomic

values. Cigánd's apróbéles (2013) and kásáskáposzta (2014) have been declared a county value by the Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County Value Register Program, the weavings of Cigánd (2021), yeast pastie with cabbage (2021), drawn pastie with cabbage (2021), cigándi green branch march (zöldágjárás) (2021) and cigándi hard csárdás (2021) (cf. www.hungarikum.hu).

As already reflected above, the power of unity in Cigánd can mobilize enormous energies, even without financial resources and central support. Local initiatives, volunteers and selfless donors have created the basis for a legacy that is nowadays being diligently perpetuated by the town's administration, talented and creative young people, local artists, natives of the town or people who have settled in Cigánd and who have taken ownership of the town's culture, and the staff of the town's cultural, educational and other institutions. Of course, the spectacular development of the town, once it had been launched, required financial support and central funding, which enabled the renovation of more buildings, giving a home to Cigánd's rich past and heritage.

Cooperation and collaboration are a priority for the city's leaders, whether in the form of city or institutional programs and events. The basic concept is always to respect and preserve traditions, including innovative activities. Looking back is always embodied in meaningful events, where the quality of an event is raised to an even higher level by tradition. Such events are the lifeblood of every institution in the city. The 100th anniversary of Cigánd, which took place from 19 August 2022 to 20 August 2023, should be highlighted as a particular occasion for preserving the town's traditions. It is of particular importance because it celebrates the centenary of the reunification of the municipality. On 19 August 2022, Teacher's House was inaugurated at Bodroghöz Museum, where the first temporary exhibition, "From Grass to Weaving", was displayed.

The nurturing and promotion of talent in the spirit of tradition

The nurturing of talent has always been present in the municipality. Just think of Sándor Román or Sándor Czigándi Varga. However, countless talented young people are still emerging in the town and the region. In addition to dance, music and drama, the visual arts are also represented. Folk dancing has a long history, but there has been a majorette group in the village for thirty years, and since 2011, classical ballet classes have been available. Talented children in all dance styles have won various prizes and awards, making their village popular and proud. The town currently has two art schools. Sárospatak Elementary Art School offers folk dance, classical ballet, and modern dance classes for talented dancers. In contrast, Sátoraljaújhely Széptan Elementary Art School offers classes in majorette, violin, piano, zither and fine arts at its Cigánd Branch.

Tradition is also present in the daily work of public education institutions. Cooperation with cultural institutions is exemplary, regardless of the person/organization running the institution. Tradition and talent management are emphasized in the city's nursery, kindergarten, and

primary schools, as well as in the county's district pedagogical service, which is part of the county's pedagogical service.

The institution, called Fairy Garden Kindergarten and Nursery of Cigánd (Cigándi Tündérvkert Óvoda és Bölcsőde) since 2017, has been preserving folk traditions in its educational activities in connection with the traditional annual festivals and everyday life. Folk games, folk tales, folk sayings, folk dances, costumes, and weaving are present in kindergarten everyday life. Organized talent workshops in the spirit of folk traditions help develop talents from an early age in many areas. The local nursery, part of the nursery school, has a vital element of this approach, with traditional activities such as folk games, stories and songs, puppet theatre, drama, and simple craft activities. The youngest children also join in folk festivities, such as St. Martin's Day celebrations or the winter bonfire. It can be said that Fairy Garden Kindergarten and Day Nursery in Cigánd incorporates a folkloristic approach in its educational program and contributes to the everyday activities of the children attending the school so that they can learn about the treasures of folklore (Cigándi Tündérvkert Óvoda és Bölcsőde Pedagógiai Programja, 2017).

The primary school was renamed after Mihály Kántor in 1998. The school's pedagogical program is based on respecting and preserving tradition. In educational work, special attention is paid to the history and traditions of the homeland, the place of residence, and the nation, awakening love for the homeland and passing on the local intellectual and material heritage. Their motto is "building a modern future rooted in progressive traditions". Their mission is to preserve tradition, shape pupils' personalities through tradition, nurture national and local culture, learn about and understand the past, and respect, cherish and appreciate its memories, traditions, and symbols. They are cultivating the spiritual heritage of Mihály Kántor, preserving the values of folk life, learning about folk dance, ethnography, and folk games, and passing them on. They have a close relationship with Bodrogeköz Museum, where they regularly visit and take part in museum educational activities.

It can be said that traditional school activities are not only at the documentary level but also permeate school and extracurricular activities. The revival of folkloric traditions and the production of festive programs on national holidays are part of this tradition and raise the profile of school and town festivities (Némethné Szendrei, 2020).

Founded in 2009 by Multipurpose Sub-Regional Association of Bodrogeköz, the pedagogical assistance service has been operating as Cigánd Division of Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County Pedagogical Assistance Service since 2013 and has been taking care of exceptionally gifted children and students since 2015. It maintains close relations with the city and region's municipality, educational institutions, and daycare centres. It maintains close links with Bodrogeköz Museum and with NGOs in the town through a separate cooperation agreement. The specialized pedagogical service uses drama pedagogical methods to manage talent among school pupils in the interpersonal talent area. This allows it to develop its traditional character. Through our activities, the local talent groups learn about the municipality's history, traditions and spiritual heritage, and the experiences and lessons learned from visits to Bodrogeköz Museum are incorporated into the talent development activities. Using the tools of drama pedagogy, they are

enriched with skills and abilities that develop not only their interpersonal but also their linguistic skills, abilities, aesthetic sense, creativity, and sense of identity. Talent development activities also involve the preschool age group. Talent development workshops in language and visual talent are organized at the Cigánd Folklore Nursery School (www.borsodszakszolgalat.hu).

The NGOs mentioned above are also active in the life of the town. In addition to Sarkantyús Folk Dance Ensemble and Csárdás Zither Orchestra, there are initiatives such as Etele Traditional Riding and Recreational Sports Association or the amateur theatre group TKMűhely, made up of teachers. The former is a regular participant in the events at Bodrogeköz Museum, where they introduce children to archery and horse-riding mysteries. The latter, as well as the folk-dance group, also perpetuate a long-standing tradition of Cigánd. The literature tells us that there was already a drama group of teachers in the village and that the school also runs a drama group for talented children. However, this is a workshop of adult amateur actors, primarily teachers, with various dramatic elements, so it is not a traditional theatre group in the traditional sense, as it is a non-traditional performance.

Cigánd is a town with a rich history and deep-rooted traditions. The town and its institutions keep the past alive and innovatively and broadly pass on the values they have created to future generations.

Summary

This study aimed to present the spiritual, cultural and gastronomic heritage of the town of Cigánd and to gather together the efforts made to preserve and transmit these traditions, which are difficult to condense into a single study since, as the text shows, Cigánd is a town with a rich past, where traditions are so deeply rooted that they permeate the daily life of the town and its institutions. Great emphasis is also placed on preserving and passing on traditions. From museum education to talent promotion, traditions are prominent in all areas. It can be said that Cigánd is constantly keeping the past alive and building the future on it. The values created in the past are widely passed on to future generations, and countless talented young people from Cigánd are setting out on a bright future, whether in education, dance, fine arts, archaeology, or medicine. Through interactive activities, children will learn about our ancestors, spiritual, material, and cultural heritage, and gastronomy.

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